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same level was registered among older participants (74.8 vs. 39.1%). In the group over 64 years old, 40.3% of them experienced a fracture due to minor trauma, while the percentage in the younger group is 15.5% ($\chi^2=36,218$; $df=1$; $p=0.000$). The TUG test can be performed by 81% of subjects. A statistically significant difference was found in the ability to perform the TUG test in relation to age ($\chi^2=72,44$; $df=1$; $p=0.000$). Women younger than 65 are able to perform this test in 94% of cases, while 64% of older participants. Among the women without fracture, 89.2% of them could perform this test, while in the subgroup with a fracture only 66.4% ($\chi^2=34,9$; $df=1$; $p=0.000$). Also, a smaller percentage of subjects with vertebral (35.6 vs. 64.4%), non-vertebral (16.5 vs. 83.5%) and both types of fractures at the same time (45.7 vs. 54.3%) are able to perform this test in the allotted time, in relation to test subjects who do not have these fractures ($\chi^2=24.6$; $df=2$; $p=0.001$). Subjects with a previous fracture of the forearm, upper arm and other fractures can perform this test in a fairly high percentage (76.8%, 64% and 70.9%), unlike subjects who had a hip fracture (41.9%)

Conclusion: Impaired walking abilities and muscle strength is associated with risk of fall among elderly women.

Reference: (1) Aleksic J, et al. Menopause 2018;25:444

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INFLUENCE OF AGE ON SLEEP QUALITY OF PHYSIOTHERAPISTS: PILOT STUDY

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Objective: To assess the effect of age on the quality of sleep of physiotherapists.

Methods: Prospective cross-section study encompassed 21 physiotherapists of both sexes, working at the Clinic for Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation of the Institute for Health Care of Children and Youth of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute (part. No.: 17/14-2023) and all subjects have signed the informative consent form. Data from a socio-demographic questionnaire (created by the examiner) and data from a sleep quality assessment questionnaire (Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index-PSQI, validated for Serbian population) were used. This questionnaire consists of two parts: 19 self-assessed questions and 5 questions assessed by a bed partner. Questions are scored from 0=no difficulty to 3=severe difficulty. Scores range from 0 to 21 (a higher score indicates poorer sleep quality), and a score >5 is considered a significant sleep disorder. Statistical processing and data analysis were done using SPSS v.23 software.

Results: In this research participated 21 respondents of both sexes, with an average age of 38.43 ± 11.28 y. Average body height was 170.24 ± 9.13 cm, and body weight was 74 ± 10.51 kg. The PSQI score values on average were 5.86 ± 2.61 . Pearson's correla-

tion coefficient determined that there is a statistically significant positive correlation between age and sleep quality of physiotherapists ($r=0.474$, $p<0.05$). The group of older respondents (over 40 y) had worse sleep quality, compared to the younger group of respondents (up to 40 y) (6.89 ± 2.57 vs. 5.08 ± 2.47), although this difference isn't statistically significant ($t=-1.629$, $p>0.05$).

Conclusion: Sleep difficulties are associated with an increased incidence of cognitive and psychomotor function disorders and workplace injuries, which is significant for all individuals (especially healthcare workers), and the risk of these disorders increases with age. It's necessary to conduct further research on a larger sample to assess how other factors such as body height, body weight, gender, years of work experience have an impact on the quality of sleep, in order to find out how it can be improved.

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PREVALENCE OF OSTEOPOROTIC FRACTURES OF THE DISTAL FOREARM IN PEOPLE OF OLDER AGE GROUP

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Objective: To study the prevalence of osteoporotic fractures of the distal forearm in people of the older age group.

Methods: The prevalence of osteoporotic fractures of the distal forearm was assessed by the attendance of patients aged 50 years and older to trauma centers in Kemerovo. 446 fractures were recorded. Among women, fractures of this location occurred in 89.01% of cases (397 people), among men in 10.99% of cases (49 people) ($p<0.0001$).

Results: The frequency of fractures of the distal forearm according to appeal was 286.75/100,000 of the population aged 50 years and older for both sexes: for men – 84.62/100,000, for women – 406.6/100,000 of the population. The analysis showed that the highest incidence of fractures of the distal forearm in women was registered at the age of 80 years and older and amounted to 680.6/100,000 person/y, the smallest number of fractures was noted at the age of 50-54 y: 94.7/100,000 person/y. years ($p<0.05$). In the age group of 55-59 y, a statistically significant trend towards an increase in the number of fractures was revealed: 347.3/100,000 ($p<0.01$). It was found that in women aged 60 years and older, no statistically significant differences between age groups were obtained ($p>0.05$). In men, the majority of fractures of the distal forearm were registered in the age groups 70-74 y, 80 y and older: 234.1/100,000 and 278.7/100,000 person/y, respectively, the smallest number of fractures occurred in the age groups 50-54 y and was 17.2/100,000 person/y ($p<0.05$). Starting from the age of 55-59 y, there was a statistically significant increase in the number of fractures in men: 79.3/100,000 person/y ($p<0.05$).

Conclusion: It was found that in women the incidence of fractures of the distal forearm was statistically significantly higher than in men. The highest incidence of fractures was recorded at the age of 80 y and older in people of both sexes.